

Protocol

The Therapeutic Role of Acupuncture in Endometriosis-Related Pain Management: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis Protocol.

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Abstract

Background: Pain is the most common and debilitating symptom of endometriosis. Unrelieved pain can deprive female patients of comfort and severely impair their quality of life and psychological health. The limitations of currently available pharmacologic treatment options make the treatment of endometriosis-related pain (ERP) a great challenge. Acupuncture has shown great potential in the management of ERP, but convincing evidence is still lacking. This systematic review aims to synthesise the latest available evidence regarding the clinical efficacy and safety of acupuncture for ERP.

Methods: A systematic literature search of seven online databases will be conducted from its inception to July 2023, including PubMed, EMBASE, Cochrane Library, Chinese National Knowledge Infrastructure, SinoMed, VIP Database, and Wanfang Database. Randomised controlled trials (RCTs) investigating the efficacy of acupuncture for ERP and meeting our predefined eligibility criteria will be included. The primary outcome of this study is the change in ERP as assessed by a validated scale, and secondary outcomes include patient quality of life, serum CA-125 levels, and adverse events. Study screening and data extraction will be conducted independently by two reviewers. The quantitative synthesis of data will be performed through RevMan 5.4 software. If applicable, subgroup analyses and sensitivity analyses will be conducted to identify potential causes of heterogeneity. The strength of evidence will be graded through the GRADE system.

Discussion: This study will critically synthesise the evidence regarding the efficacy and safety of acupuncture for the treatment of ERP. The findings will influence evidence-based management decisions for clinicians in the treatment of ERP.

PROSPERO registration number CRD42023442373.

Keywords: Acupuncture; Endometriosis; Chronic Pelvic Pain; Systematic Review; Meta-analysis; Protocol; Traditional Chinese Medicine; Dysmenorrhea; Ectopic Endometrium; Evidence-based Medicine.

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1. Introduction

Endometriosis is a common chronic, inflammatory and oestrogen-dependent disease characterised by the presence of endometrial-like tissue outside the uterus¹⁻³. Ectopic tissue causes immune cell infiltration and inflammation, which in turn lead to sensitisation of nociceptive paths, making women susceptible to pain and infertility⁴. It is estimated that nearly 10 percent of women of reproductive age are afflicted by this condition, and the prevalence is as high as 50 percent among women seeking infertility treatment^{5,6}.

However, the exact prevalence of endometriosis is uncertain as it requires laparoscopy or surgical visualisation for a definitive diagnosis ⁷.

Chronic pain, including dysmenorrhea, dyspareunia, and non-menstrual pelvic symptoms, is the most common and debilitating symptom of endometriosis ^{1,8,9}. It is reported that approximately 70%-90% of patients with pelvic pain are associated with endometriosis ¹⁰. The pathogenesis of pain production is complex, and possible mechanisms are related to chronic inflammation, recurrent bleeding from the lesion, and peripheral and central nervous sensitisation caused by abnormal growth of lesion tissue ^{6,11,12}. Persistent pain is recognised as a potentially disabling condition that affects the quality of life, mental health, sexuality, and productivity of women ¹³⁻¹⁶, and carries a heavy financial burden ¹⁷. A multi-centre prospective study across Europe and the USA found that the average total annual cost per woman with endometriosis, including the cost of healthcare and lost productivity, was close to €10,000 ¹⁸.

Guideline-recommended first-line pharmacologic treatment for endometriosis-related pain (ERP) primarily includes nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs) and progestin-containing oral contraceptives ⁹. However, a recent Cochrane systematic review showed insufficient evidence to support that NSAIDs are effective in managing endometriosis pain ¹⁹. In addition, prolonged use of contraceptives and progestin tends to cause drug resistance as well as bothersome side effects, such as irregular uterine bleeding, weight gain, and mood swings, which can lead to discontinuation of drug therapy ²⁰⁻²³. Surgical therapy is a potential method of ERP management after failed pharmacologic therapies, however, pain symptoms usually recur within 6 to 12 months after surgical treatment ^{1,24}. Consequently, the management of pain in patients with endometriosis usually requires repeated medications or multiple surgeries until menopause ^{9,25,26}. Concerns about the limited efficacy and side effects of conventional therapies make many pain patients seek complementary treatments with anti-inflammatory and analgesic effects.

Acupuncture, a traditional non-pharmacological therapy, involves the insertion of needles into the body to treat diseases. The World Health Organization (WHO) 2019 global report states that acupuncture is the most widely used traditional medical therapy in the world ²⁷. Acupuncture is widely used for pain management in many countries around the world and is becoming increasingly popular. In recent years, growing evidence has supported the use of acupuncture as an effective intervention for ERP management ^{28,29}. Moreover, clinical guidelines refer to acupuncture as a potential approach for ERP management and suggest that clinicians should discuss non-pharmacological treatment strategies such as acupuncture with ERP patients who are seeking pain treatment. However, the guidelines criticised the quality of evidence from previous studies and rejected recommendations for any specific non-pharmacological interventions for ERP, including acupuncture ^{27,30}.

In recent years, an increasing number of high-quality RCTs have investigated the efficacy of acupuncture for ERP ^{31,32}, and integrating these potentially eligible RCTs into the latest meta-analyses to update previous evidence is necessary. Therefore, we will conduct a meta-analysis of currently available RCTs to assess the efficacy of acupuncture for ERP.

2. Methods

2.1. Study registration

This protocol followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analysis Protocol (PRISMA-P) statement and has been registered at PROSPERO (No. CRD42023442373) ³³.

2.2. Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Type of study

All published RCTs investigating the effects of acupuncture for ERP will be included in this review. In addition, if there is a cross-over trial, we will include only pre-cross-over

data to avoid carry-over effects. There are no restrictions on language or publication date. Case reports, reviews and animal experiments will be excluded.

Type of participants

Subjects will be women of reproductive age with a diagnosis of endometriosis confirmed by laparoscopy or surgery, all of whom have pain related to endometriosis not due to pre-existing pathologies or related to treatment. Studies will be excluded if the diagnosis of endometriosis cannot be confirmed by laparoscopy or histology.

Type of interventions and comparators

The only permitted experimental treatment is acupuncture, which can be used alone or in combination with a control intervention. In order to minimise heterogeneity in data synthesis from a clinical perspective, acupuncture in this study will be defined as traditional or modern acupuncture techniques involving needle insertion (eg, manual acupuncture and electroacupuncture). Therefore, non-invasive acupuncture techniques will be excluded, such as acupressure, moxibustion, and transcutaneous electrical stimulation. Differences in acupuncture materials, acupoint selection, and treatment duration will not be taken into account. Interventions in the control group will be conventional western medications such as NSAIDs, progestin, GnRH agonists, and contraceptives, with detailed reporting of dosage, and treatment duration. Studies comparing different acupuncture methods or comparing acupuncture with other non-pharmacological therapies will not be considered.

Types of outcomes

Primary outcomes: The primary outcome will be the change in endometriosis-related pain, including dysmenorrhea, non-menstrual pelvic pain, and dyspareunia, and the pain score will be measured by validated pain-related scale such as the visual analogue scale (VAS) and the numeric rating score (NRS).

Secondary outcomes: (1) Quality of life, measured by ERP-specific scales (such as the Endometriosis Health Profile (EHP) pain scores) or any validated health-related scale (such as the Patient Global Impression of Change (PGIC)). (2) Serum CA-125 levels, measured before and after acupuncture treatment using an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay. (3) Adverse events, to assess the safety of acupuncture for ERP, we will record the occurrence of adverse events in the included trials.

2.3. Search methods for identification of studies

We will conduct a comprehensive search for available RCTs in three English online databases (PubMed, EMBASE, and Cochrane Library) and four Chinese online databases (SinoMed, VIP, Chinese National Knowledge Infrastructure and Wanfang database). The search time for each electronic database ranges from database establishment to July 2023. The following keywords by both Medical Subject Headings (MeSH) and free words will be used: "endometriosis"; "endometrioses"; "endometrioma"; "endometriomas"; "endometrio*"; "dysmenorrhea"; "dyspareunia"; "dyschezia"; "pelvic pain"; "dysuria"; "constipation"; "pain symptom"; "pain"; "acupuncture"; "electroacupuncture"; "electro-acupuncture"; "ear acupuncture"; "needling"; "Intradermal acupuncture"; "warm acupuncture"; "fire acupuncture". All available combinations of search terms will be used to maximise the comprehensiveness of the final included trials. Additionally, the reference lists of prior relevant narrative reviews and meta-analyses in this clinical topic will also be checked to minimise any possible omissions.

2.4. Data collection and analysis

Study selection

Data retrieved from each database will be imported into Endnote X9 software to delete duplicate documents. To ensure the comprehensiveness of the included studies and

minimise subjective influence, two independent investigators will review the titles, abstracts, and full text of the literature to identify eligible studies based on predetermined inclusion and exclusion criteria. Any disagreements about study selection will be resolved through a third investigator arbitration.

Data extraction

Two independent researchers will use a standardised spreadsheet to extract the following data from all eligible studies: (I) general information (first author, language, country, article title, publication year, study type, study design, number of centres, sample size and follow-up period); (II) patient information (average age, gender distribution, diagnosis, pain intensity before treatment); (III) intervention details (types of acupuncture, acupoint selection and treatment duration/ frequency/ session); (IV) comparator details (drug type, drug dose and treatment frequency/ session); (V) outcomes (primary and secondary outcomes, measured time points and data). If a study provides unclear or insufficient data, the corresponding author will be contacted for details. Any discrepancies raised will be resolved by a third investigator.

2.5. Quality assessment

The quality of the included trials will be assessed by two independent reviewers using the Cochrane Risk of Bias 2 (ROB2) tool based on the following five domains: (1) randomisation process, (2) deviations from intended interventions, (3) missing outcome data, (4) measurement of the outcome, and (5) selection of the reported results. The ROB for each item will be classified into three levels (low risk, high risk, and some concerns) based on the specific circumstances of the study, and the overall ROB for the assessment results will be predicted accordingly. Any dispute between the two reviewers will be resolved by consulting with a third reviewer for a final decision.

2.6. Data synthesis and analysis

Data analysis

The software RevMan (V.5.3) will be the primary instrument for data analysis, which will be used to measure the 95% confidence intervals (CIs) for treatment effects. The effect measures will be presented as risk ratios (RR) for dichotomous data and weighted mean difference (WMD) or standardised mean difference (SMD) for continuous data. The WMD will be used when the outcome indicator is measured using the same assessment scale or instrument, otherwise, the SMD will be used. Data pooling will be performed using the Mantel-Haenszel method and the inverse variance method for dichotomous and continuous data, respectively^{34,35}.

Assessment of heterogeneity

Statistical heterogeneity between studies will be calculated using the Cochrane Q test and I^2 statistic³⁶. A P -value of >0.1 and $I^2 <50\%$ is a prerequisite to using a fixed-effects model for pooled analyses, and this heterogeneity is considered acceptable; conversely, it indicates statistically significant heterogeneity between studies, and meta-analyses will be more conservatively assessed using a random-effects model. Subgroup or sensitivity analyses will be conducted to investigate possible sources of heterogeneity from both clinical and methodological perspectives. Narrative analysis of the data will be performed when quantitative synthesis is not appropriate.

Subgroup analysis

If heterogeneity is significant and available data are sufficient, we will explore the sources of clinical heterogeneity through subgroup analyses, which will be based on the following: (1) different acupuncture techniques (eg, hand acupuncture, electroacupuncture, auricular acupuncture, or warm acupuncture); (2) different acupuncture interventions (eg, acupuncture and acupuncture combined with drugs); (3) the initial severity of pain; and (4) the course of acupuncture treatment.

Sensitivity analysis

If subgroup analyses exclude the sources of clinical heterogeneity, a sensitivity analysis will be used to assess the robustness of the Meta-analysis results. This test will attempt to check whether any particular study contributes to the majority of the heterogeneity. In addition, the potential impact of statistical models on the robustness of the results will also be considered.

Publication bias

If no fewer than 10 trials reported the same outcome indicator, funnel plots will be generated to assess potential reporting bias by visual examination. Egger's regression test will be used to assess its asymmetry³⁷.

Grading the quality of evidence

Two reviewers will independently assess the certainty of evidence using the GRADE system³⁸. In accordance with the GRADE rating criteria, the assessment will determine the quality of evidence into four levels (high, moderate, low, or very low) based on five domains (risk of bias, inconsistency, indirectness, imprecision and publication bias). Any disputes will be resolved by a third reviewer.

2.7. Ethics and dissemination

Ethical approval is not required for this study and the findings will be published in a peer-reviewed journal.

3. Discussion

Endometriosis is an under-diagnosed and disabling condition in which pain is the dominant symptom and the most commonly reported symptom in primary care settings³⁹. The chronic nature and varied presentation of pain seriously affect the quality of life of patients with endometriosis, which emphasises the importance of adequate medical support for pain management⁴⁰. However, currently available first-line treatments often fail to reduce pain symptoms to a satisfactory degree with unpleasant side effects and high recurrence rates⁴¹. In addition, a recent multicentre retrospective cohort study found that 45.4% of endometriosis patients were dissatisfied with their medical support, including pain management⁴⁰. As a result, finding other effective alternative treatments for pain management is becoming an urgent priority for endometriosis patients.

Acupuncture, a traditional Chinese medicine therapy with a history of more than 3,000 years, has been widely used for chronic pain management due to its favourable analgesic effects and lack of side effects. Therefore, acupuncture is considered a potentially valuable complementary therapy to existing pain management strategies⁴². With the global popularity of acupuncture therapy, research on the mechanisms of acupuncture analgesia has received extensive attention. Recent studies have provided laboratory-based evidence suggesting that acupuncture analgesia is a complex process involving the entire nervous system from periphery to centre⁴³. Potential mechanisms of acupuncture analgesia may be associated with the interaction of multiple bioactive molecules in the pain process, including inflammatory mediators, neurotransmitters, neuropeptides, and cell signalling molecules, etc.⁴²⁻⁴⁴.

Currently, acupuncture has been widely used clinically in the management of endometriosis pain. Although previous systematic reviews have attempted to assess the therapeutic effects of acupuncture for ERP^{45,46}, however, the quality of evidence from previous studies is limited by the quality and number of included studies. With an increasing number of new RCTs published in recent years, it is necessary to update a systematic review in the field to generate more conclusive evidence of acupuncture for ERP. Inevitably, this systematic review may have some limitations. First, the methodological quality of the included original studies may affect the accuracy of the results in this study. Second, differences in the type of acupuncture and treatment protocols among the included studies may lead to significant clinical heterogeneity.

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